

EFFECT OF JALAUKAVACHARANA (MEDICINAL LEECH THERAPY) IN DUSHTA VRANA (NON-HEALING FOOT ULCER): A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Jalaukavacharna or Medicinal Leech Therapy or Hirudotherapy is an old technique of bloodletting and is being widely studied by many researchers for possible effects on numerous diseases as Dushta Vrana Ropana, inflammatory diseases, osteoarthritis, various diseases according to different Doshas etc. Detailed description of the Jalaukavacharna and Jalauka is given in Sushruta Sutra Sthana Thirteen. Researchers have described various properties of leech therapy like anti-inflammatory, analgesics, platelet inhibitory, anticoagulant etc. 65 years old male patient with history of DMII since 15 years came to Gopabandhu Ayurvedic College and Hospital Puri, Odisha with the complaints of chronic non-healing wound over right foot greater toe on posterior aspect having slight serous discharge and

smell. After thorough debridement, leech therapy was done for 8 weeks, followed by weekly twice for two weeks and once a week for next 6 weeks. Strict limb elevation was advised along with strict diabetic management. The treatment followed may be adopted in the future for various cases.

KEYWORDS: Wound, Dushta Vrana, Leech therapy, Jalaukavacharn.

INTRODUCTION

In this scenario, modern medicine is on its peak, but nothing can beat Indian Ancient Medicine. Acharya Sushruta “The Father of Surgery” defined Vrana as phenomenon causing

destruction or rupture or discontinuation of tissue in a particular part of the body which is termed as Vrana leading to discoloration. A wound which does not heal or heals very slowly though best efforts has been taken, known as Dushta vrana. There is a natural course of wound healing but Vrana which does not heal in its natural healing time along with other pathological manifestation is known as Dushta Vrana. Acharya Sushruta has described signs and symptoms of Dushta Vrana. Sushruta described Dushta Vrana as widened or concised, very hard, very soft, elevated or depressed, very cold or very warm, black, red, white, having either of the color, having purulent discharge and smell includes Mansa, Sira, Snayu, having foul smell, pustular discharge, exudates creating abnormal paths, elevated with overgranulated tissue, ugly looking and unpleasant smell, accompanied by severe pain, burning sensation, suppuration, redness, itching and swelling, various eruptions and various other complications, amantate vitiated blood and with long time persistence are the features of Dushta Vrana.

Detailed description of types of Jalauka is present in Sushruta Samhita. Sushruta has described Jalauka in Sushruta Sutra¹³ in Jalaukavacharna Adhyaya.¹² types of Jalauka have been described by Acharya out of which 6 are poisonous (Savisha) and 6 are non-poisonous(Nirvisha). Sushruta Sutra Sthana, Adhyaya thirteenth and fourteenth speaks about various methods of bloodletting along with use of medicinal leech therapy to treat painful inflammatory conditions and also seen effective in diabetic foot management. In ongoing scenario many researches are going on leech to access its properties, bioactive substances, mode of action, breeding, storage etc. as this is one of the elaborated and interesting topics of research.

Leeches secrete more than 20 identified bioactive substances such as Antistasin, Eglins, Gaumerin, Hirudin, Saratin, Bdelellins, Complement and Carboxypeptidase Inhibitors, etc.

Chemical constituents of saliva of Leeches i) Hirudin: Anticoagulant.

ii)Hyaluronidase:breaks down Hyaluronic acid, the bonding material of connective tissue, thus fostering the flow of blood and fluids from affected areas.

Mode of action of Hirudotherapy: It promotes the improvement of blood circulation in the tissues, renders thrombolytic, anti-inflammatory, immunostimulating action, raises nutrition of tissues, and strengthens tissues immunity. Biologically active substances containing in saliva of medicinal leeches can restore blood circulation in the nidus of inflammation, remove an ischemia of organs, and provide capillary tissue exchange and due to it can carry out the

transport of chemical drugs into the nidus of inflammation, improve immune protection and regeneration of tissues.

One chemical called, Hirudin, inhibits the conversion of fibrinogen to fibrin by inhibiting thrombin & preventing blood from clotting. Hirudin also inhibits platelet aggregation. Hirudin works in conjunction with a vasodilator, one that increases the diameter of blood vessels by relaxing the smooth muscle of the blood vessels, to widen the diameter of the vessel and increase the flow of blood and by that promotes blood flow.

Therapeutic properties of hirudotherapy: Bloodletting, Anticoagulant, Protective antithrombotic, Thrombolytic, Correction of micro-circulation disorders, Anti-Ischemic, AntiInflammatory, Local anti-edematous, Anti athero-sclerotic, Immunostimulating, Anti-oxidant.

Diabetic foot ulcer is most devastating complication of diabetes mellitus, while affecting 15% of diabetic patients throughout their life. Classical triad of neuropathy, ischemia and infection are characteristics of Diabetic foot. Almost 85% of the amputations are preceded by diabetic foot ulcers. Number of risk factors for the development of foot ulcers have been suggested, the most important being peripheral sensory neuropathy followed by peripheral vascular diseases. The proportion of neuropathic, neuroischemic and purely ischemic lesions in diabetics is 54, 34, 10% respectively.

Infection in a diabetic foot is a limb threatening condition because the consequences of deep infection in a diabetic foot are more disastrous than elsewhere mainly because of certain anatomical peculiarities. The foot has several compartments, which are intercommunicating and the infection can spread from one into another and lack of pain allows the patient to continue ablation further facilitating the spread.

Meggitt's Classification of Diabetic Foot

Grade 0-Foot pain only

Grade 1-Superficial ulcer of the foot

Grade 2-Deep ulcer of the foot

Grade 3-Ulcer with bone involvement

Grade 4-Forefoot gangrene

Grade 5-Whole foot gangrene

Early effective management of DFU and advanced strategies can reduce the severity of complications such as escapable amputation and possible mortality and this can also upgrade overall quality of life. Multidisciplinary team should evaluate the patient of DFU as holistic approach to wound management required.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The main aim of the study is to evaluate the efficacy of Jalaukavacharna (Leech therapy) in the management of Dushta Vrana (non healing ulcers).

CASE STUDY

A 65 years old male patient came to Out Patient Department of Shalya Tantra Department GAM Puri with complaints of a chronic deep wound over posterior aspect of greater toe of right foot with serous discharge and bad smell having occasionally pain over affected area. Patient has known history of Diabetes Mellitus and on medications since 15years. History of previous treatment at regional medical college was also given by the patient. On examination.

Wound was open with slight serous discharge and foul smell discolored greater toe with pain. Complete blood examination was done followed by proper debridement of the wound. Patient was admitted to the male ward of Shalya Tantra at Gopabandhu Ayurveda Mahavidyalaya & Hospital Puri, Odisha.

History of Past Illness: Patient has type II Diabeties mellitus since 15 years and on continuos medication.

Treatment

After thorough debridement of the wound on the very first day, leech therapy was followed weekly twice for 2 weeks and once a week for next 6 weeks along with daily dressing of the wound (scraping of unhealthy granulated tissues as per requirement) with conventional method. Anti-hyperglycemic drugs were given as previously with continous monitoring on blood glucose level and other blood investigations.

Materials Used For Jalaukavacharna

Jalauka, Haridra powder (Turmeric powder), Sterilised gauze picese, dressing pads, cotton, gloves, disposable syringe, kidney tray, Distilled water, Normal saline, Needle, Sterilised non-toothed forceps, Scissors, Container of sterile water (To keep the leech after procedure) which will be labaled with patient's name & date.

Method

Patient was undergone total 10 sittings of Jalaukavacharna first four sittings was done as per weekly twice and remaining six sittings as once in a week on OPD basis. Jalaukavacharna was done in standard protocol as described by Acharya Sushruta.

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

Wound was because of diabetic foot gangrene thus irregular in shape, with discoloration, slough, swelling, serous discharge and foul smell and unhygienic in nature. After use of leech therapy new healthy granulation tissue started appearing, wound margins contracted in healthy manner and there was reduction in slough formation, discharge, smell and discoloration around the wound.

Leech attached with the initial usually painless bite, and sucked between 10-20 mL Of blood in the attachment of 25 to 45 minutes.

DISCUSSION

Sushruta mentioned Raktavisravana in the cases of Dushtarakta. Jalaukavacharna is the type of Rakta Visravana hence helps to remove Dushta Rakta which is responsible for various inflammatory conditions.

Sushruta in Chikitsa Sthana Sadhyovrana Chikitsa Adhyaya mentioned Raktamokshana in Prameha and Kushtha Dushta Vrana.

With the advancements of science and Technology the mechanism of leech how it work have started to be clarified. After the leech bite, the tissues and blood vessels allow access to the hyaluronidase and collagenase enzymes; action of histamine like molecules leads to vasodilatation; platelet inhibition. Its therapeutic benefits are not from blood removed during the bite but from the saliva which contain anticoagulants and vasodilators.

Leech saliva includes various bioactive substances like hyaluronidase which is a spreading factor and has antibiotic properties. Hirudin a potent anticoagulant, enables the blood flow by inhibiting blood coagulation by binding to thrombin. Callin inhibits blood coagulation by blocking the the binding of von willebrand factor to collagen. Destabilase dissolves fibrin and has thrombolytic effects. Bdelins has anti-inflammatory effect and inhibits trypsin, plasmin acrocin. Acetylcholine is a vasodilator. Eglins are anti-inflammatory, inhibits activity of alpha-chymotrisin, chymase, elastase, substilisin and cathepsin G. Factor Xa-inhibitors inhibits the

activity of coagulation factor Xa. Collagenase reduces collagen. Carboxypeptidase-A inhibitor increases the inflow of blood.

CONCLUSION

This leech therapy which has been used by our Acharyas since ages, now getting tremendous recognition because of its quality of removing venous insufficiency, restoration of venous outflows, pain management, wound healing in infected-noninfected Chronic wounds etc. Detailed study is needed to evaluate the elaborated effect of leech therapy on wound healing.

BEFORE TREATMENT

DURING TREATMENT

DURING TREATMENT

AFTER TREATMENT

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